

**A REVIEW OF THE STABILITY STUDIES AND QUALITY ASSURANCE OF
PHARMACEUTICAL PRODUCTS ACROSS SUPPLY CHAIN SYSTEMS IN NIGERIA**

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ABSTRACT

Regulating drug quality throughout distribution is a crucial process. Medicines come in a variety of dose forms, such as pills, syrups, injectable, etc., each of which must be kept under specific environmental conditions based on drug stability. Pharmaceutical supply chain in Nigeria suffers many challenges that hinder the proper provision of medicines. This review discussed the elements including structural, regulatory and logistical issues that affect the stability and quality assurance of pharmaceutical products across different supply chains in Nigeria, and proffers solutions to the identified challenges. A thorough literature search was systematically carried out amongst the top recent articles in reputable journals and World Health Organization (WHO) publications in which topics on the supply chains and their challenges on quality assurance of pharmaceutical products, especially in Nigeria were published. Findings from recent articles revealed that a thorough grasp of supply chain administration is required in order to handle the distribution of medicines appropriately. Literature findings also revealed that unauthorized pharmaceutical distribution chains in Nigeria contribute to poor stability and quality assurance of pharmaceutical products across supply chains in Nigeria. In contrast to Nigeria, pharmaceutical supply chains in the UK, USA, and India maintain stricter controls during distribution to ensure medicine availability without increasing wastage. Self-inspections should be carried out to track the application and adherence to Good Distribution Practice and to make necessary recommendations. Correctional and preventative actions are essential to maintaining compliance and product quality throughout the supply chain. The recommended documentation system should comprise data, procedures, instructions, protocols, contracts, records, certificates of analysis, and product specifications, particularly for importers, and should be accessible for auditing and regulatory inspection. Effective supply chain management and planning are required to ensure product availability while minimizing waste across pharmaceutical supply chain stages.

KEYWORDS: Stability Studies, Nigeria, supply chain, stability testing, quality assurance.**1.0 INTRODUCTION**

A Pharmaceutical Supply Chain (PSC) is defined as a combination of processes, organizations, and operations involved in the development, design, manufacturing, storage, and distribution of pharmaceutical products (Kenji Goyit *et al.*, 2020). The PSC is considered unique because it directly affects human life and health, making efficiency and reliability critical (Kudirat *et al.*, 2022). Proper functioning of the PSC ensures that medicines reach end users safely and in good quality (Ammann Claude, 2011). The PSC comprises several interconnected actors, including suppliers,

manufacturers, wholesalers, distributors, pharmacies, and healthcare facilities (Olutuase *et al.*, 2022). The pharmaceutical supply chain involves four major activities: product selection and procurement, inventory management, storage and distribution, and service delivery to patients (Chukwu *et al.*, 2018). These activities require continuous monitoring and evaluation to ensure efficiency and quality assurance (Mohammadkarim Bahadori *et al.*, 2024).

Access to essential medicines is highly dependent on a well-functioning supply chain capable of transporting

products efficiently from manufacturers to end users (WHO, 2020). Drugs may undergo degradation during transportation and storage, which necessitates stability assessment throughout the distribution process (Ammann Claude, 2011). It is, therefore, considered good practice to evaluate the stability of drug substances and drug products in accordance with International Council for Harmonisation (ICH) guidelines Q1A–Q1E and Q5C, as well as World Health Organization stability testing recommendations (WHO, 2018). Stability testing programs typically begin with stress studies designed to identify degradation pathways and establish appropriate analytical methods (Sultana & Mohammed, 2018). Drug substance stability studies are subsequently conducted under long-term and accelerated storage conditions to determine degradation behavior over time (WHO, 2018).

Ensuring that pharmaceutical products via supply chains reach patients without loss of therapeutic efficacy is a major concern for both manufacturers and regulatory authorities (Ammann, 2011). An increasing number of pharmaceutical and biotechnological products, including vaccines and biologics, require strict temperature-controlled distribution systems to maintain product quality (Amarauche, 2021). Disruptions such as transportation delays and inadequate temperature control can expose products to temperature excursions that compromise stability (Ammann Claude, 2011). This poses significant challenges for manufacturers in Nigeria and other developing countries, particularly once products leave controlled distribution channels and enter pharmacies, hospitals, or patient homes (“Wide Spectra of Quality Control,” 2011).

The pharmaceutical supply chain in Nigeria, therefore, grapples with significant challenges, including regulatory inefficiencies, infrastructural limitations, and systemic inadequacies, which collectively undermine effective medication quality control (Eruaga *et al.*, 2024). These issues often lead to the proliferation of substandard and counterfeit medications, jeopardizing public health outcomes and eroding trust in the healthcare system (Eruaga *et al.*, 2024). A significant consequence of these challenges is the compromised pharmacopoeial quality of drugs, exacerbated by factors such as widespread counterfeiting, excessive decomposition of active ingredients due to environmental conditions, and inadequate quality assurance during manufacturing (Eruaga *et al.*, 2024; Taylor *et al.*, 2001). This situation raises concern in emerging economies like Nigeria, where the clinical and economic burdens associated with poor-quality medicines are substantial (Kudirat *et al.*, 2022). This review, therefore, aims to comprehensively examine the current state of stability studies and quality assurance practices for pharmaceutical products within Nigerian supply chains, identifying key challenges and proposing evidence-based recommendations for improvement (Eruaga *et al.*, 2024; Leghari *et al.*, 2025).

2.0 Overview of the Pharmaceutical Supply Chain in Nigeria

The pharmaceutical supply chain refers to the coordinated system of processes involved in the sourcing, manufacturing, storage, distribution, and delivery of medicines to end users (World Health Organization [WHO], 2022). In Nigeria, the pharmaceutical supply chain plays a critical role in ensuring access to safe, effective, and quality-assured medicines for the population (Olutuase *et al.*, 2022). The effectiveness of this supply chain directly influences public health outcomes and the overall performance of the healthcare system (Chukwu *et al.*, 2018).

The Nigerian pharmaceutical supply chain is composed of several interconnected stakeholders, including manufacturers, importers, wholesalers, distributors, pharmacies, healthcare providers, and regulatory authorities (Olutuase *et al.*, 2022). Manufacturers are responsible for producing pharmaceutical products in accordance with national and international quality standards to ensure safety and efficacy (National Agency for Food and Drug Administration and Control [NAFDAC], 2024). Local manufacturing is supplemented by importation due to limited domestic production capacity, making Nigeria heavily dependent on imported medicines (Chukwu *et al.*, 2018).

Following production or importation, wholesalers and distributors play a central role in transporting pharmaceutical products to healthcare facilities and retail outlets across the country (Buseri *et al.*, 2023). These actors are responsible for inventory management, warehousing, and maintaining appropriate storage conditions to preserve product stability during distribution (WHO, 2020). Inefficiencies at this stage, including inadequate storage facilities and poor transportation infrastructure, can compromise drug quality and availability (Olutuase *et al.*, 2022).

Pharmacies, including community and hospital pharmacies, serve as the final point of medicine distribution to patients (Buseri *et al.*, 2023).

Healthcare providers such as physicians and nurses are integral to the pharmaceutical supply chain through prescribing, administering, and monitoring drug therapy (WHO, 2020).

Regulatory oversight of the pharmaceutical supply chain in Nigeria is primarily the responsibility of the National Agency for Food and Drug Administration and Control (NAFDAC) (NAFDAC, 2024).

Despite regulatory efforts, the Nigerian pharmaceutical supply chain continues to face challenges such as fragmented distribution networks, weak enforcement mechanisms, and limited cold chain capacity (Amarauche, 2021). These challenges increase the risk of drug degradation, particularly for temperature-sensitive

products such as vaccines and biologics (WHO, 2020). Addressing these systemic weaknesses is critical to improving medicine availability, quality assurance, and healthcare outcomes nationwide (Olotuase *et al.*, 2022).

3.0 Possible sources of degradation of tablets during supply chain

3.1 Temperature

Temperature is one of the most critical factors influencing the stability of pharmaceutical products during the supply chain (Sultana & Mohammed, 2018). An increase in temperature accelerates chemical reaction rates, leading to faster degradation of drug substances (Zothanpuii *et al.*, 2020). Elevated temperatures are known to enhance hydrolytic and oxidative degradation pathways, thereby reducing the potency of active pharmaceutical ingredients (WHO, 2018). Inadequate temperature control during storage and transportation can therefore result in loss of drug efficacy and shortened shelf life (Amarauche, 2021).

3.2 Moisture

Moisture exposure significantly affects the stability of solid dosage forms, particularly tablets (Zothanpuii *et al.*, 2020). Water absorption by hygroscopic drugs or excipients can initiate hydrolysis and cause physical changes such as swelling, cracking, or dissolution of tablets (Sultana & Mohammed, 2018). High humidity conditions during storage and distribution may lead to loss of mechanical strength and altered dissolution profiles of tablets (WHO, 2018). Effective moisture control through appropriate packaging and storage conditions is therefore essential to maintain tablet stability throughout the supply chain (WHO, 2020).

3.3 pH

The pH of the environment plays a significant role in the degradation rate of many pharmaceutical compounds (Sultana & Mohammed, 2018). Drugs susceptible to hydrolysis exhibit maximum stability only within a specific pH range (Zothanpuii *et al.*, 2020). Deviations from the optimal pH can accelerate degradation reactions and reduce drug potency (WHO, 2018). Buffer systems are commonly employed in formulations to maintain pH within the range of maximum stability during storage and distribution (Sultana & Mohammed, 2018).

3.4 Excipients

Excipients can influence drug stability through both physical and chemical interactions with active pharmaceutical ingredients (Zothanpuii *et al.*, 2020). Excipients such as starch and povidone may contain residual moisture that promotes hydrolytic degradation of drugs (Sultana & Mohammed, 2018). Incompatibilities between excipients and drug substances can result in reduced stability and formation of degradation products (WHO, 2018). Proper selection and compatibility testing of excipients are therefore critical steps in formulation development to ensure stability throughout the supply chain (Zothanpuii *et al.*, 2020).

3.5 Oxygen

The presence of oxygen can facilitate oxidative degradation of susceptible drug substances (Sultana & Mohammed, 2018). Oxidation reactions often involve free radical mechanisms that lead to loss of potency and formation of harmful degradation products (Zothanpuii *et al.*, 2020). Exposure to oxygen during manufacturing, packaging, storage, or transportation increases the risk of oxidative instability (WHO, 2018). Strategies such as replacing oxygen with inert gases like nitrogen or carbon dioxide in packaging can significantly enhance drug stability (Sultana & Mohammed, 2018).

3.6 Light

Light exposure is another important factor contributing to drug degradation during the supply chain (Zothanpuii *et al.*, 2020). Photosensitive drugs undergo photochemical reactions that can result in discoloration, reduced potency, or complete degradation (Sultana & Mohammed, 2018). Ultraviolet and visible light can initiate these reactions, particularly during prolonged exposure (WHO, 2018). The use of light-protective packaging materials such as amber glass containers and opaque blister packs is an effective strategy to minimize photodegradation during storage and distribution (WHO, 2020).

4.0 Mechanism of Drug Degradation

Drug products, regardless of dosage form, are inherently susceptible to degradation over time during storage and distribution (Sultana & Mohammed, 2018). Degradation may result in physical changes such as discoloration or precipitation, as well as chemical alterations that reduce drug potency or compromise safety (Zothanpuii *et al.*, 2020). The extent and type of degradation depend largely on the chemical structure of the drug substance and the environmental conditions to which it is exposed (WHO, 2018). Several degradation mechanisms have been identified, including hydrolysis, oxidation, isomerization, photochemical degradation, and polymerization (Sultana & Mohammed, 2018). Some pharmaceutical compounds may undergo more than one degradation pathway simultaneously, increasing the risk of instability during the supply chain (WHO, 2018).

4.1 Hydrolysis

Hydrolysis is one of the most common mechanisms of drug degradation and involves chemical cleavage of a compound by reaction with water (Sultana & Mohammed, 2018). Drugs containing functional groups such as esters, amides, lactams, lactones, imides, or carbamates are particularly susceptible to hydrolytic degradation (Zothanpuii *et al.*, 2020). Examples of drugs prone to hydrolysis include acetylsalicylic acid, physostigmine, and methyldopa (Sultana & Mohammed, 2018). Hydrolysis may be catalyzed by hydrogen ions under acidic conditions or hydroxyl ions under basic conditions, as well as by buffer species present in formulations (WHO, 2018).

To reduce hydrolytic degradation, drugs are often formulated at a pH corresponding to their maximum stability (Sultana & Mohammed, 2018). The use of non-aqueous solvents such as alcohols, glycerin, or propylene glycol can also reduce water availability and slow hydrolysis (Zothanpuii *et al.*, 2020). Additional stabilization strategies include reducing drug solubility, forming drug complexes, or incorporating suitable excipients that limit moisture exposure (WHO, 2018).

4.2 Oxidation

Oxidation is another major pathway of drug degradation and may occur concurrently with hydrolysis (Sultana & Mohammed, 2018). Oxidative degradation involves the loss of electrons or hydrogen atoms, or the addition of oxygen, resulting in chemical transformation of the drug molecule (Zothanpuii *et al.*, 2020). This process often proceeds through free radical chain reactions initiated by factors such as light, heat, or trace metal contaminants (WHO, 2018). Drugs containing phenolic or catechol structures, including morphine, epinephrine, and methyl dopa, are particularly susceptible to oxidation (Sultana & Mohammed, 2018).

Preventive measures against oxidation include storage under anaerobic conditions by replacing oxygen in containers with inert gases such as nitrogen or carbon dioxide (Zothanpuii *et al.*, 2020). Avoiding metal containers that may catalyze oxidation and incorporating antioxidants or reducing agents into formulations are also effective stabilization strategies (WHO, 2018). Lowering storage temperatures further reduces the rate of oxidative reactions and enhances product stability (Sultana & Mohammed, 2018).

4.3 Isomerisation

Isomerisation refers to the conversion of a drug molecule into a different structural or optical isomer with reduced or no therapeutic activity (Sultana & Mohammed, 2018). This process may involve geometric or optical changes and can significantly affect drug efficacy (Zothanpuii *et al.*, 2020). Certain drugs, such as adrenaline, can undergo racemization from an active isomer to a less active form, resulting in reduced therapeutic effect (Sultana & Mohammed, 2018). Isomerisation reactions may be accelerated under acidic conditions or in the presence of light (WHO, 2018).

Vitamin A is another example of a compound that can isomerize from its active all-trans form to less effective cis isomers during storage (Zothanpuii *et al.*, 2020). Controlling environmental conditions such as pH, temperature, and light exposure is essential to minimize isomerisation during the supply chain (WHO, 2018).

4.4 Photo-Chemical Degradation

Photochemical degradation occurs when drug substances absorb light energy, leading to chemical reactions that alter molecular structure (Sultana & Mohammed, 2018). These reactions may be oxygen-dependent, such as

photo-oxidation, or oxygen-independent, including rearrangement and dimerization reactions (Zothanpuii *et al.*, 2020). Photosensitive drugs exposed to ultraviolet or visible light may undergo rapid degradation, resulting in loss of potency or formation of toxic products (WHO, 2018).

Sodium nitroprusside, used in the treatment of acute hypertension, is a notable example of a photosensitive drug that requires protection from light to maintain stability (Sultana & Mohammed, 2018). Other drugs susceptible to photodegradation include phenothiazines, hydrocortisone, and ascorbic acid derivatives (Zothanpuii *et al.*, 2020). Protective measures such as the use of amber-colored containers, opaque packaging, aluminum foil overwraps, and storage in dark environments are effective strategies to prevent photochemical degradation during storage and distribution (WHO, 2020).

5.0 Objectives of Stability Studies

The primary objective of stability testing is to provide evidence on how the quality of a pharmaceutical product varies over time when exposed to environmental factors such as temperature, humidity, and light (WHO, 2018). These studies generate scientific data that support decisions regarding appropriate storage conditions and handling requirements during the supply chain (Sultana & Mohammed, 2018).

Another key objective of stability testing is to establish the shelf life and retest period of drug substances and finished pharmaceutical products (WHO, 2018). Shelf-life determination ensures that products remain safe and effective for patient use until the expiration date (Sultana & Mohammed, 2018).

6.0 Importance of Stability Studies

Stability studies are essential to ensure that pharmaceutical products maintain their intended quality, safety, and efficacy throughout their shelf life (Sultana & Mohammed, 2018). Instability of active pharmaceutical ingredients may result in reduced drug concentration, leading to under-dosing and therapeutic failure in patients (Zothanpuii *et al.*, 2020). Loss of stability can compromise treatment outcomes and undermine confidence in healthcare systems (WHO, 2020).

During drug degradation, toxic or harmful by-products may be formed, posing serious risks to patient safety (Sultana & Mohammed, 2018). Such degradation products may cause adverse reactions or long-term health effects if administered unknowingly (WHO, 2018). Stability studies therefore play a critical role in identifying and controlling degradation pathways that could lead to toxicity (Zothanpuii *et al.*, 2020).

Physical instability, including changes in appearance, color, or consistency, can also affect patient acceptability and compliance (Sultana & Mohammed, 2018). Stability

testing applies principles of chemical kinetics to predict degradation behavior and estimate product shelf life under various environmental conditions (WHO, 2018). These predictive tools enable manufacturers to design robust formulations and storage conditions that minimize quality deterioration (Zothanpuii *et al.*, 2020).

Conducting comprehensive stability studies helps protect the reputation of pharmaceutical manufacturers by ensuring that marketed products remain fit for use throughout their declared shelf life (Bahadori *et al.*, 2024). Assurance of consistent product quality enhances regulatory compliance and strengthens public trust in pharmaceutical systems (WHO, 2022).

7.0 Types of Drug Stability

7.1 Physical Stability

Physical stability refers to the ability of a pharmaceutical product to retain its original physical properties throughout its shelf life (Sultana & Mohammed, 2018). These properties include appearance, color, odor, taste, hardness, brittleness, particle size, and dissolution characteristics (Zothanpuii *et al.*, 2020). Any undesirable physical changes may affect patient acceptability, dosing accuracy, and overall therapeutic effectiveness (WHO, 2020). Maintaining physical stability is therefore essential during formulation, manufacturing, packaging, storage, and distribution of pharmaceutical products (Sultana & Mohammed, 2018).

7.2 Chemical Stability

Chemical stability is defined as the ability of a drug product to maintain its chemical integrity and labeled potency within specified limits throughout its shelf life (Zothanpuii *et al.*, 2020). Chemical degradation of drugs may occur through reactions such as hydrolysis, oxidation, photolysis, and isomerization, leading to reduced therapeutic activity (Sultana & Mohammed, 2018). Degradation can also result in the formation of potentially harmful by-products that compromise patient safety (WHO, 2018). Solid dosage forms are generally more chemically stable than liquid formulations due to reduced molecular mobility and lower water content (Zothanpuii *et al.*, 2020).

7.3 Microbiological Stability

Microbiological stability refers to the resistance of a pharmaceutical product to microbial contamination and proliferation during storage and use (WHO, 2020). Microbial contamination can lead to product spoilage, reduced efficacy, and serious health risks to patients (Sultana & Mohammed, 2018). Dosage forms with high moisture content, such as aqueous solutions and semi-solid preparations, are particularly susceptible to microbial growth (Zothanpuii *et al.*, 2020). The use of antimicrobial preservatives, aseptic manufacturing processes, and appropriate packaging are critical measures for ensuring microbiological stability (WHO, 2018).

7.4 Therapeutic Stability

Therapeutic stability refers to the ability of a drug product to maintain its intended clinical effect throughout its shelf life (Sultana & Mohammed, 2018). Loss of therapeutic stability may occur even in the absence of visible physical or chemical changes if degradation reduces pharmacological activity (WHO, 2020). Ensuring therapeutic stability is essential to achieve consistent treatment outcomes and avoid therapeutic failure (Zothanpuii *et al.*, 2020).

7.5 Toxicological Stability

Toxicological stability refers to the absence of significant increases in toxicity during the storage and use of a pharmaceutical product (Sultana & Mohammed, 2018). Degradation processes may generate toxic impurities that were not present in the original formulation (WHO, 2018). Stability studies are therefore necessary to monitor impurity profiles and ensure that toxic degradation products remain within acceptable safety limits throughout the product's shelf life (Zothanpuii *et al.*, 2020).

8.0 Challenges in the Pharmaceutical Supply Chain

8.1. Regulatory Issues

The pharmaceutical supply chain in Nigeria operates within a highly regulated environment overseen by national regulatory agencies (NAFDAC, 2024). Despite the presence of regulatory frameworks, challenges such as delays in drug registration and approval processes persist (Olutuase *et al.*, 2022). Inconsistent enforcement of quality standards across the supply chain has contributed to the circulation of substandard and counterfeit medicines in the Nigerian market (Nwosu *et al.*, 2024). These regulatory weaknesses pose significant risks to patient safety and undermine confidence in the healthcare system (WHO, 2022). Limited regulatory capacity and inadequate post-marketing surveillance further hinder effective oversight of pharmaceutical distribution activities (Chukwu *et al.*, 2018). Strengthening regulatory enforcement and harmonizing inspection practices are therefore critical to improving supply chain integrity and medicine quality (WHO, 2020).

8.2. Logistical Challenges

Logistical inefficiencies represent a major barrier to effective pharmaceutical supply chain performance in Nigeria (Chukwu *et al.*, 2018). Poor road networks, unreliable transportation systems, and inadequate storage facilities complicate the timely distribution of medicines, particularly to rural and hard-to-reach areas (Olutuase *et al.*, 2022). These infrastructural challenges increase the likelihood of delays, stockouts, and product damage during transit (WHO, 2020). Inadequate cold chain infrastructure poses a serious challenge for temperature-sensitive pharmaceutical products such as vaccines and biologics (Amarauche, 2021). Failure to maintain appropriate storage and transport conditions can lead to drug degradation and reduced therapeutic efficacy

(WHO, 2020). Weak inventory management systems also contribute to medicine wastage and expiry across different levels of the supply chain (Bahadori *et al.*, 2024).

8.3. Economic Factors

Economic instability significantly affects the availability and affordability of pharmaceutical products in Nigeria (Bahadori *et al.*, 2024). Fluctuations in currency exchange rates increase the cost of imported medicines, placing financial strain on healthcare providers and patients (Olutuase *et al.*, 2022). Limited funding for public healthcare facilities further restricts their ability to maintain adequate medicine stocks (Chukwu *et al.*, 2018). High operational costs associated with transportation, storage, and regulatory compliance also impact supply chain efficiency and product pricing (WHO, 2022). These economic constraints reduce purchasing power, limit access to essential medicines, and exacerbate health inequities within the population (WHO, 2020).

13.0 Recommendations

To optimize the pharmaceutical supply chain in Nigeria, several strategies can be implemented:

- 1. Strengthening Regulatory Frameworks:** is essential to enhance quality assurance and supply chain integrity within Nigeria's pharmaceutical sector (NAFDAC, 2024). Increasing regulatory capacity and improving enforcement mechanisms will help reduce the prevalence of substandard and counterfeit medicines (WHO, 2022).
- 2. Investment in Infrastructure:** Investment in transportation infrastructure and storage facilities is necessary to improve medicine distribution, particularly in rural and underserved areas (WHO, 2020). Enhancing cold chain capacity will further protect temperature-sensitive products from degradation during distribution (Amarauche, 2021).
- 3. Collaboration among Stakeholders:** Promoting collaboration among government agencies, pharmaceutical manufacturers, distributors, and healthcare providers can improve coordination and efficiency across the supply chain (Bahadori *et al.*, 2024). Multi-stakeholder partnerships support resource sharing and joint problem-solving to address systemic challenges (WHO, 2022).
- 4. Embracing Technology:** Embracing digital technologies for inventory management, tracking, and communication can significantly enhance supply chain transparency and responsiveness (WHO, 2022). Capacity-building initiatives aimed at training healthcare and supply chain personnel are also critical for sustaining long-term improvements (Buseri *et al.*, 2023).

14.0 CONCLUSION

The pharmaceutical supply chain in Nigeria faces multiple interconnected challenges that affect medicine quality, availability, and public health outcomes

(Olutuase *et al.*, 2022). Therefore, issues related to regulation, logistics, economic constraints, and stability management continue to undermine supply chain effectiveness.

Implementing evidence-based strategies, strengthening regulatory oversight, and adopting technological innovations can substantially improve supply chain performance and resilience in Nigeria. Addressing stability-related risks throughout the supply chain is essential to ensuring that safe, effective, and high-quality medicines reach patients across Nigeria.

Conflict of interest

Authors declare no conflict of interest.

REFERENCES

- Amarauche, H. C. (2021). *Quality assessment of cold chain storage practices for pharmaceuticals in Nigeria*. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Policy and Practice*, 14(1): 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40545-021-00380-9>
- Ammann Claude., (2011) "Stability Studies Needed to Define the Handling and Transport Conditions of Sensitive Pharmaceutical or Biotechnological Products," *AAPS PharmSciTech*, vol. 12, no. 4. Springer Science+Business Media, p. 1264, Sep. 26, 2011. doi: 10.1208/s12249-011-9684-0.
- Chukwu, O. A., Ezeanochie, M. C., & Alabi, B. N. (2018). *Poor performance of medicines logistics and supply chain systems in Nigeria*. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Health Services Research*, 9(4): 289–296. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jphs.12253>
- Eruaga, M. A., Itua, E. O., & Bature, J. T. (2024). enhancing medication quality control in nigeria: a comprehensive analysis of regulatory challenges and solutions. *International Medical Science Research Journal*, 4(3): 284. <https://doi.org/10.51594/imsrj.v4i3.920>
- Kudirat, M. B., Danraka, A., & Abdulmujeeb, A. (2022). The Public Health Consequences of Substandard Medicines in Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Pharmacy*, 56(2). <https://doi.org/10.51412/psnjp.2022.43>
- Kenji Goyit, Kennedy I. Amagon and Dauda A. Dangiwa (2020). An assessment of drug supply chain system in selected facilities in Nigeria. *West African Journal of Pharmacy*, 31(2): 45–56. <https://doi.org/10.60787/wajpcp-27-1-103>
- Leghari, Q. A., Noshad, Anwar, N., Syed, Y., Shuja, A. A., & Ali, M. (2025). Ensuring Pharmaceutical Quality: The Role of Stability Studies and Regulatory Guidelines: A Review [Review of *Ensuring Pharmaceutical Quality: The Role of Stability Studies and Regulatory Guidelines: A Review*]. *Indus Journal of Bioscience Research.*, 3(3): 112. <https://doi.org/10.70749/ijbr.v3i3.942>
- Mohammadkarim Bahadori, Ehsan Teymourzadeh, Sajjad Bahariniya, Ali Tahernezhad & Gholamreza

- Poorheidari (2024). Factors Affecting the Pharmaceutical Supply Chain: A Systematic Review. *Health Scope*, 13(2): 1-9.
9. National Agency for Food and Drug Administration and Control (NAFDAC). (2024). *Good Storage and Distribution Practice (GSDP) guidelines for pharmaceutical products*. NAFDAC. https://www.nafdac.gov.ng/wp-content/uploads/Files/Resources/Guidelines/PMS_Guidelines_2024/NAFDAC-Good-Storage-and-Distribution-Practice-Guidelines-For-Pharmaceutical-Products-1.pdf
 10. National Agency for Food and Drug Administration and Control (NAFDAC). (2021). *Good Cold Chain Management Guidelines for Vaccines and Biopharmaceutical Products*. NAFDAC. https://www.nafdac.gov.ng/wp-content/uploads/Files/Resources/Guidelines/Updated_Drug_Guidelines/NAFDAC-GOOD-COLD-CHAIN-MANAGEMENT-FOR-VACCINES-BIOPHARM.-PRODUCTS-GUIDELINES-2021-DETER-GDL-017-01.pdf
 11. Nwosu, M. C., Nworu, C. S., & Egejuru, R. O. (2024). *Quality of essential medicines from different sources in Enugu and Anambra, Nigeria*. *BMC Pharmacology and Toxicology*, 25(1): 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40360-024-00698-8>
 12. Okafor U.G., Ekeocha, Z. Bryn S., K. Clase K, and Shiihii S (2022) “Development of an Assessment Tool for Good Distribution Practice for a Regulatory Agency in West Africa,”. doi: 10.5703/1288284317576.
 13. Olutuase, D. O., Chukwu, E. E., Adeleke, A., & Alenoghena, I. O. (2022). *Medicines and vaccines supply chains challenges in Nigeria: A scoping review*. *BMC Public Health*, 22(1): 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-021-12361-9>
 14. Saba Sultana & Shahid Mohammed (2018). A Review on Stability Studies of Pharmaceutical Products. *International Journal for Pharmaceutical Research Scholars (IJPRS)*, 7(1): 28-49.
 15. Taylor, R. B., Shakoor, O., Behrens, R. H., Everard, M. L., Low, A. M., Wangboonskul, J., Reid, R., & Kolawole, J. (2001). Pharmacopoeial quality of drugs supplied by Nigerian pharmacies. *The Lancet*, 357(9272): 1933. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736\(00\)05065-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736(00)05065-0)
 16. Timi Fiekumo Buseri, Tolulope Olajumoke Aremu, & Ismail Ayinla Suleiman (2023). Knowledge And Practice Of Supply Chain Management Of Pharmaceuticals. *African Journal Of Pharamceutical Research*, 15(2): 91-100.
 17. Wide Spectra of Quality Control. (2011). In *InTech eBooks*. <https://doi.org/10.577>
 18. World Health Organization. (2022). *Guidelines: Distribution — Quality assurance of pharmaceutical products throughout the supply chain*. WHO. <https://www.who.int/teams/health-product-and-policy-standards/standards-and-specifications/norms-and-standards-for-pharmaceuticals/guidelines/distribution>
 19. World Health Organization. (2020). *TRS 1025 — Annex 7: Good storage and distribution practices for medical products*. WHO. <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/978-92-4-000182-4>
 20. World Health Organization. (2018). *TRS 1010 — Annex 10: WHO guidelines on stability testing of active pharmaceutical ingredients and finished pharmaceutical products*. WHO. <https://www.who.int/publications/m/item/trs1010-annex10>
 21. Zothanpuui F, Rajesh R & Selvakumar K (2020). A Review On Stability Testing Guidelines Of Pharmaceutical Products. *Asian Journal of Pharmaceutical and Clinical Research*, 13(10): 3-9.